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THE DIFFERENT FOREIGN POLITICAL VECTOR OF THE SOUTH CAUCASUS COUNTRIES IN THE POST-SOVIET PERIOD AS A FACTOR HINDERING REGIONAL INTEGRATION

Abstract. The purpose of the conference topic is to analyze in detail the political, cultural, economic and social issues in the Caucasus region. Let's clearly see its momentousness in the formation of the European geopolitical space and the challenge of modern regional defense. This topic presents the political transformation, geopolitical and strategic situation in the South Caucasus area, make a comparison with the current events in the international arena. The paper will talk over the perspectives of regional integration. We will also analysis the political orientation of the Caucasus countries, neighborly relations and conflicts. Here we will refer to the volume of energy resources importance in the formation of foreign policy. We will get acquainted with the latest decisions made in the region and beyond.

The South Caucasus region is not only geopolitically noteworthy, but also important in many ways, both for the East and the West, as well as for the modern world. The role of the Caucasus has always been and is still the major strategic area between the East and the West.

The issue of security has always been the leading research article of international relations. At the same time, there is an opinion that the policy made by countries is one of the main decisive factors in determining the international situation. That is why the stages of its development have been become even more interesting in the conditions of the new transformation of the international political system.

Keywords: The South Caucasus, Foreign Affairs, Integration, European Union, International Relations.

In 1992, Georgia took its first steps towards the West and became a member of the North Atlantic cooperation Council. The next step was 1994, when Georgia joined to NATO program "Partnership for Peace." Despite all this, it took a long time for Georgia to express its desire for full membership, which happened in 2002.

In 2003, many things changed in Georgia. With the change of the president, the foreign vector of the country changed fundamentally. What we mean is that Georgia has strictly decided on a pro-Western course. This had results, and in 2004, Georgia became the first country to create an Individual Partnership Action Plan (IPAP) from NATO. This program was created for those countries that were ready to deepen cooperation with NATO.

The Georgian government decided to send troops to Iraq and at the same time join NATO operations in Afghanistan. The number of Georgian soldiers in Iraq exceeded 2000, which was the third largest contingent after the United States of America and the United Kingdom.

Relations gradually deepened. In 2005, NATO sent officers to Georgia, which was followed by the opening of the NATO Liaison Office.

The next step was in 2006, when the NATO Foreign Ministers' meeting laid the foundation for an intensive dialogue, which meant consultations on different issues, including political and security issues, defense, conflict resolution, economy and other significant disputes.

The most important moment for Georgia was the year 2008, when it successfully fulfilled its obligations, which was followed by the transfer of the Action Plan (MAP) to Georgia from NATO. All this should have happened at the Bucharest summit. These are the years when Georgia was known as one of the most active participants in US and NATO operations and certainly had more troops in Iraq and Afghanistan than most member states.

But everything did not happen as it seemed. It should be clarified that the granting of MAP did not necessarily mean membership in the organization, but it was one of the requisite conditions. It seems that the opponents of granting MAP to Georgia appeared, among them Germany is the most notable. After that, some opinions appeared, including that German Chancellor Angela Merkel had a negative attitude towards the President of Georgia.

This cannot be considered as the main reason, because we should not forget the interests of Russia in relation to Georgia. It should not be surprising that at that time the German representatives put their country's interests ahead of ours. The Germans did not want to spoil bilateral relations with Russia. In the end, Georgia failed to get the well-deserved MAP, despite the many efforts of the Bush administration, the Germans still stood their ground. Georgia was promised that it would definitely become a member of NATO, but without any indication of time.

In 2011, Georgia officially received the title of NATO aspirant country. In 2014, Georgia was named as an interoperable partner of NATO. Also, Georgia was awarded the status of the country of increased opportunity along with Jordan, Australia, Finland, and Sweden.

In the middle of all this was the most difficult period for Georgia. The war 2008 Russia against to Georgia. There were conversations about the war started part. All this was done not only after the end of the war, but also during the war.

Compared to Georgia, Russia had much larger resources covered a lot of issues as a result of its implementation. Although the majority of countries condemn Russia in the war with Georgia, we also find opinions where part of the responsibility rests with Georgia. Of course, there is a political motive behind these opinions and Russia is hidden behind the curtain. Supporters of this opinion do not want to spoil relations with Russia, and on the contrary, with this action, they try to warm Russia's attitude towards them.

Finally, on August 7, 2008, Russian military forces invaded Georgia. All this was done without Georgia's permission or its notification, which in itself implies an act of aggression according to international law. This invasion continued until a cease-fire agreement was signed between the parties on August 12.

Since the 1990s, the European Union has shown great interest in the South Caucasus region. The European Union began to take steps as the appointment of special representatives in the region, due to the fact that the European Union realized the very important geopolitical

situation of the South Caucasus region. The actions taken by the European Union once again indicated that it was ready for close cooperation and partnership with the region. As an example of this, we can cite many support projects adopted by the European Union. By this we mean providing humanitarian, financial and technical assistance to Georgia, Azerbaijan and Armenia through various projects. Among these programs, the Neighborhood Policy adopted in 2004 and the Eastern Partnership launched in 2013 are noteworthy. The main goal of the latter was, in the South Caucasus region, to increase the rule of law, protect human rights, strengthen democracy and resolve the active or frozen conflicts in the region in a peaceful way.

Since gaining independence, South Caucasus countries (Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia) have different foreign policy priorities. Nevertheless, each country has established clearly defined relations with the European Union. The leaders of the country, on different historical phases, expressed their opinions regarding the European Union and expressed their readiness for the prospects of integration with it.

The conflicts in the South Caucasus region are one of the hindering factors in relations with the European Union. This situation hinders the development of democratic processes in those countries that are representatives of the neighborhood policy program. Here, we must emphasize the insinuation and determination of the EU member states, which should be able to make transformative changes in solving the mentioned problematic issues. In order to solve the mentioned problem, the European Union needed a platform different from the "neighborhood policy", which would be more efficient and effective. That is why the European Union has developed a new format for Eastern European countries called "Eastern Partnership". The task of this format was multi-functional mutual cooperation in the long term.

The European Union, through the format of the Eastern Partnership, made a distinction between the countries of the Black Sea and the Southern Mediterranean region. This is explained based on the specifics of each country. It should be noted that the Eastern Partnership did not affect Russia. He refused to participate in the neighborhood policy platform. This was evidenced by the fact that the processes taking place in Russia became visible to everyone, how human rights were being violated, democratic institutions were regressing, and foreign policy was being evaluated negatively. Therefore, after the discovery of such facts, mutual cooperation between Brussels and Russia would not be possible in any way. The current events in Russia were completely contrary to the founding principles of the European Union.

Relations between the countries of the South Caucasus and the European Union are moving forward. The EU is gradually increasing both financial and moral support to these countries. With this, he tries to gain his influence in this region. Especially important is the fact that Brussels focuses on cooperation in the field of energy, which aims at the safe transportation of Caspian Sea oil for the European market.

In 2003, the European Council adopted a document called the European Security Strategy, in which it is stated that the goal of the European Union is the economic and political

stable development of the South Caucasus region, to achieve which the organization will participate more actively. The European Union has actively engaged in deepening cooperation with the region within the framework of the "European Neighborhood Policy" program. This is confirmed by the offer of an "action plan" for the countries of the South Caucasus.

The 2008 war caused a lot of damage to Georgia, but it never stopped wanting to join NATO. In August 2008, the NATO Foreign Affairs Ministers established the Georgia-NATO Commission (NGC), whose main goal is practical cooperation between Georgia and NATO. NATO gives directions and recommendations to Georgia in various directions. At the same time, Georgia annually presents to NATO about the reforms implemented in Georgia, which relate to the integration into the Euro-Atlantic organization.

Finally, we can say that Georgia deserves to join NATO. We belong to the European family with our identity. We think about the mistakes we have made and the most difficult path we have taken, and despite all this, we still want to walk on the European democratic path. Georgia has confirmed our serious attitude towards integration into the Euro-Atlantic space many times, which was demonstrated by the implemented reforms and participation in NATO missions over the years. It should also be noted that Georgia's membership is included in NATO's goals, as it will contribute to the settlement of the situation in the Black Sea region, which implies the stabilization of the energy benefits and transport highways that this region can provide to Europe as a whole.

As for Armenia, in the spring of 2018, the Velvet Revolution took place in Armenia, as a result of which Nikol Pashinyan took the post of Prime Minister. The fact that Pashinyan managed to fully exercise his power became interesting, because the majority in the Armenian parliament was still represented by the ruling party. This meant that they could remove the prime minister at any moment. All this was prevented by the public's full support for Pashinyan. The situation has completely changed after early parliamentary elections were held in Armenia. Pashinyan's party managed to get the majority of votes (70.42%), thereby fully establishing control over the parliament.

The state of Armenia is not distinguished by its own energy resources. They get gas mainly from Russia, as evidenced by the fact that 83% of imported gas is Russian gas.

This emphasizes Armenia's attitude towards Russia. Here, it is worth noting the fact that Armenia accumulated a lot of debts during this import and had to hand over strategically important objects to Russia. Of course, all this had an impact on Armenia's foreign policy. The world saw all this clearly in 2013, when Armenia refused to sign the association agreement with the European Union. Which in itself meant the rejection of the "Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area Agreement" (DCFTA). In Novo-Ogaryovo near Moscow, the then president of Russia and Armenia, Serzh Sargsyan, reached an agreement. According to which, Armenia is ready to join the customs union of Russia, Belarus and Kazakhstan. We can explain this problem by the fact that there is no gas in Armenia, and at the same time, the rulers of the country at that time did not want to irritate Russia.

The European Union has always considered the territory of the South Caucasus as the territory of Europe. The area between the Middle East and Central Asia. It should be noted that this territory was never vitally important for the European Union, but it was never indifferent to it. When the Soviet Union collapsed, the European Union signed a partnership and cooperation agreement with the countries of the South Caucasus. What followed was the implementation of the neighborhood policy on the region. Although the Armenian government was forced to withdraw from the EU in 2013, they still managed to sign an enhanced and comprehensive partnership with the EU. It entered into force in March 2021.

Since the independence of Armenia, Iran has been considered as a friendly state. This was confirmed by the fact that in the ongoing Karabakh war in 1992-1994, Iran mainly chose a balanced policy. Even after the Karabakh war, Iran and Armenia continued friendly relations, as evidenced by the Iran-Armenia gas pipeline launched in 2007.

Based on all of the above, the new government will have to develop a new regional policy to respond to the challenges. Regardless of Iran's attitude towards the Karabakh war, it is necessary to develop an effective strategy so that Armenia can restore relations with Iran. The priority of this issue became obvious when the free trade space between the Eurasian Union and Iran was opened. This once again gave great importance to Armenian-Iranian relations. It is probably most advantageous for Armenia to offer Russia and Iran a tripartite format, Armenia-Iran-Russia, which will be very similar to the format of Azerbaijan-Iran-Russia. Also, Armenia should somehow try to join the Iran-China economic agreement with its Iranian and Chinese partners. In which once again it is necessary to maintain good relations with Iran. In general, Armenia cannot allow its relations with Iran to deteriorate.

Since the 1990s, Azerbaijan's foreign policy priorities have remained largely unchanged. Its main task is to restore territorial integrity, strengthen the country's independence and develop a strong regional economic partnership.

At the crossroads of global powers, where Azerbaijan is landed, its foreign policy goals, cannot be achieved alone. It is with these natural resources that Azerbaijan is able to strengthen its economy. Infrastructure and defense projects became a priority. Nevertheless, the war with Armenia showed Azerbaijan the needness that is called partner states. It was necessary to develop regional cooperation frameworks.

It is in this direction that Azerbaijan has developed several important foreign policy priorities.

Azerbaijan's first priority is to refrain from joining military alliances and maintain de-facto neutrality in the region. Azerbaijan did not join the Russian-led Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) and was one of the first former Soviet republics without Russian military presence. Azerbaijan has a similar approach to NATO. It has no aspiration to become a member of NATO, unlike its regional partners, we mean Georgia and Ukraine. Instead, it focuses on

practical cooperation with NATO and its member states. Which is mainly done within the framework of the Partnership for Peace program.

Since 2009, Azerbaijan has been cooperating with the European Union within the framework of the Eastern Partnership (EAP) program in both bilateral and multilateral formats. While bilateral cooperation with the EU remains a priority, the multilateral platform of the EAP allows Azerbaijan to pursue its interests in the context of regional politics.

As Azerbaijan focused more on the Middle East, it realized the benefits that would come from having strong ties with the Islamic countries of the Middle East. One important factor in this is, of course, the common religion of Islam. Azerbaijan is an active member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and frequently hosts high-level committee meetings.

The three states of the Middle East, which are Turkey, Iran and Saudi Arabia, are important partners for Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan managed to balance relations with these countries until now. He has often avoided tensions over sensitive issues such as relations with Israel, the war in Syria or competing regional energy projects.

We must definitely touch on the impact of the gas factor on Azerbaijan's foreign policy. Among the countries of the South Caucasus, only Azerbaijan is distinguished by the surplus of energy resources. As of 2018, Azerbaijan's gas reserves are 1.3 trillion cubic meters.

The economic income of the country is the extraction, processing and export of these resources. By obtaining these resources, Azerbaijan was able to modernize its "hard power" military force. According to SIPRI FACT SHEET, in 2017, the annual military budget of Azerbaijan amounted to two billion dollars. Azerbaijan's national security concept document noticed the following that any kind of attack on its energy resources will be perceived as a violation of national security.

The gathering of European and American investments in the energy sector in Azerbaijan gave the state an opportunity to get rid of Russia. These investments contributed to the development of energy resources. He also developed such an important pipeline as the construction of the "South Caucasus Gas Pipeline", which, as everyone knows, passes through the territories of Turkey and Georgia. In the future, this pipeline, together with the Trans-Anatolian (TANAP) and Trans-Adriatic (TAP) pipelines, should supply Europe with Azerbaijani gas.

These gas projects have not only economic, furthermore international importance for the state. What we mean is the establishment of Azerbaijan as a modern state. In addition to the economic aspect, the benefit was that Azerbaijan would gain the reliable country status.

CONCLUSION

The South Caucasus, with its geopolitical location, has always been of great interest to the world's "big players". The development and stability of the region is influenced by both the processes taking place within the region and the world eventuation.

Since independence, in many cases their interests have intersected with the West despite their varied of foreign policy. All this has become the biggest challenge for them. In the conditions

of the formation of the new world order in the world, the situation between the United States of America and the Russian Federation is particularly tense, which of course also concerns the South Caucasus region. Along this, new competitors have appeared in the region, driven by their own interests and ambitions in relation to the South Caucasus.

The most important matter is how countries of this region will manage international integration, which is actually not possible in the near future. The countries of the South Caucasus must respond quickly and effectively to the existing challenges.

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